

FREQUENCY OF PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE ABUSERS AMONG FIRST TIME PSYCHIATRIC ADMISSIONS

Dr. Anhum Malik^{*1}, Dr. Syed Muhammad Akram Hamdani², Dr. Shandana Qazi³

^{*1}Post-graduate Resident, Psychiatry, CMH, Peshawar

²Associate Professor Psychiatry and Consultant Psychiatrist, CMH Lahore

³Senior Registrar Psychiatry, Rehman Medical Institute, Peshawar

¹anhummalik@outlook.com, ³shandana.qazi@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19492608>

Keywords

Psychoactive substance abuse, cannabis, amphetamines, cocaine, opioids, sedatives and pain medications

Article History

Received: 17 June 2025

Accepted: 03 July 2025

Published: 18 July 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Anhum Malik

Abstract

Background: Psychoactive substance abuse has been a well-recognized problem globally. The widespread abuse of psychoactive substances has far-reaching consequences, affecting individuals' physical and mental health, relationships, and overall well-being, as well as placing significant burdens on society.

Objective: To determine the frequency of psychoactive substance abusers among first time psychiatric admissions in psychiatry ward, CMH, Peshawar.

Material & Methods: This was cross sectional study, conducted from (15 February 2025 to 15 June 2025) on 65 patients, presenting and being first time admitted to the psychiatry ward of Combined Military Hospital, Peshawar. Data on substance abuse was collected via an interviewer assisted questionnaire (Annex 1 and 2). Data was collected by the trainee herself and confidentiality was assured during the data collection process. Data was analyzed using SPSS 20. Mean and standard deviation or median were used to measure quantitative variables like age and were measured after checking the normality of data by sharpio wilk test whereas frequencies and percentages were used to measure qualitative variables including gender, occupational status, co-morbidities and data collected by the self-administered ASSIST version 3.0. for dependence on tobacco products, alcoholic beverages, cannabis, cocaine, amphetamine-type stimulants, inhalants, sedatives, hallucinogens, opioids etc. Types of substance abuse were stratified against age, gender etc. Post stratification Chi-square or Fisher's exact test were applied to check the significance of results at 5% level of significance.

Results: Our study was conducted on 65 cases, presenting and being first time admitted to the psychiatry ward of Combined Military Hospital, Peshawar. Among our 65 total study cases, Tobacco products dependence was found in 41 (63.1%) cases, Alcoholic beverages dependence was found in 7 (10.8%) cases, Cannabis dependence was found in 52 (80%) cases, Cocaine dependence was found in 10 (15.4%) cases, Amphetamine type stimulant dependence was found in 4 (6.2%) cases, Inhalants dependence was found in 5 (7.7%) cases, Sedatives dependence was found in 16 (24.6%) cases, Hallucinogens dependence was found in 6 (9.2%) cases and Opioids dependence was found in 14 (21.5%) cases.

Conclusion: A high frequency of moderate to high-risk use of various psychoactive substances, including tobacco, cannabis, opioids, and sedatives, was

observed among patients with first-time psychiatric admissions. These findings suggest that substance use is commonly present in this population and may be associated with psychiatric morbidity. Therefore, there is a need to enhance community awareness regarding substance use and strengthen preventive strategies, including appropriate regulatory and public health measures.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoactive substance abuse has been a well-recognized problem globally. The widespread abuse of psychoactive substances has far-reaching consequences, affecting individuals' physical and mental health, relationships, and overall well-being, as well as placing significant burdens on society.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) are a set of 17 goals that were built to address the aspects involved to ensure a safe and thriving future for the world. Among these, SDG3.5 states: "Strengthen the prevention and treatment of substance abuse, including narcotic drug abuse and harmful use of alcohol". This signifies that addressing the issue of substance abuse is vital for ensuring a healthy life for people all across the globe¹.

The abuse of psychoactive substances has significant social, economic and health implications. Drug abuse can strain health care systems, lead to loss of productivity, increase crime rates and contribute to the spread of infectious diseases, especially in cases of intravenous drug use. To mitigate these issues, governments worldwide have implemented various approaches to regulate psychoactive substances. This study aims to assess the expanse of substance abuse in an urban center using WHO's Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST)⁵. Moreover, it can further help to devise policies to limit and control the harmful impacts of substance abuse on both individual as well as institutional level.

OBJECTIVE:

To determine the frequency of psychoactive substance abusers among first time psychiatric admissions in psychiatry ward, CMH Peshawar.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS:

Psychoactive substance abuse: It includes history of alcohol and illicit drugs such as cannabis, amphetamines, cocaine, opioids, and non-prescribed psychoactive prescription medications like sedatives and pain medications, used over the last 3 months. The frequency of psychoactive substance abuse assessed using WHO's Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST) (Annex 2)⁵.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Setting: Department of Psychiatry, Combined Medical Hospital, Peshawar

Duration of study: 15 February 2025 to 15 June 2025

Sampling technique: Non-probability consecutive sampling

Sample size: Sample size of 65 calculated using OpenEpi Version 3 calculator with the following assumptions:

Expected prevalence of cannabis abuse in first time psychiatric admissions is 5.8%⁴Confidence interval of 95% Absolute precision of 5.7%

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged 15-45 years, of either gender (male/females), who were being admitted to the psychiatry ward for the first time.

Exclusion criteria: History of co-morbidities like Diabetes, Hypertension, Epilepsy or Asthma

Data collection: Data was collected by trainee after approval from hospital administration, supervisor and ethical committee and after taking informed consent from patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria, presenting to Psychiatry department of Combined Military Hospital, Peshawar. Basic demographic details were measured such as age, gender, marital status,

education, occupation and socioeconomic status. Data on substance abuse was collected via an interviewer assisted questionnaire (Annex 1 and 2). All the data was collected by the trainee herself and confidentiality was assured during the data collection process.

Data Analysis:

Data was analyzed using SPSS 20. Mean and standard deviation or median was used to measure quantitative variables like age and was measured after checking the normality of data by sharpio willk test whereas frequencies and percentages was used to measure qualitative variables including gender, occupational status, comorbidities and data collected by the self-administered ASSIST version 3.0. for dependence on tobacco products, alcoholic beverages, cannabis, cocaine, amphetamine-type stimulants, inhalants, sedatives, hallucinogens, opioids etc. Type of substance abuse was stratified against age, gender etc. Post stratification Chi-square or Fisher's exact test was applied to check the significance of results at 5% level of significance.

RESULTS AND TABLES:

In this study, Among 65 cases, mean age was 29.17 ± 7.62 years, all (100%) of this cases were males, 41 (63.1%) cases were employed and 24 (36.9%) cases were un-employed, 40 (61.5%) cases were married and 25 (38.5%) cases were single, 18 (27.7%) cases had low socioeconomic status, 42 (64.6%) had intermediate socioeconomic status and 5 (7.7%) had high socioeconomic status, 17 (26.2%) cases had

primary education, 40 (61.5%) cases had secondary education and 8 (12.3%) had higher education, 34 (52.3%) cases had co-morbidities and 31 (47.7%) cases had no co-morbidity.

Among 65 total study cases, Tobacco products dependence was found in 41 (63.1%) cases, Alcoholic beverages dependence was found in 7 (10.8%) cases, Cannabis dependence was found in 52 (80%) cases, Cocaine dependence was found in 10 (15.4%) cases, Amphetamine type stimulant dependence was found in 4 (6.2%) cases, Inhalants dependence was found in 5 (7.7%) cases, Sedatives dependence was found in 16 (24.6%) cases, Hallucinogens dependence was found in 6 (9.2%) cases and Opioids dependence was found in 14 (21.5%) cases.

Stratifications of Tobacco products dependence, Alcoholic beverages dependence, Cannabis dependence, Cocaine dependence, Amphetamine type stimulant dependence, Inhalants dependence, Sedatives dependence, Hallucinogens dependence and Opioids dependence was done with regards to age groups, occupational status, marital status, socioeconomic status, education and comorbidities.

Stratification analyses revealed no statistically significant differences in substance dependence across age, occupational status, marital status, socioeconomic status, or comorbidity (all $p > 0.05$). Education level was the only exception, with higher tobacco dependence in secondary/higher education and higher opioid dependence in primary/secondary education groups ($p = 0.02$ and $p = 0.01$, respectively).

Table – 01: Frequency of Tobacco products dependence among study cases

Tobacco products dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	41	63.1
No	24	36.9
Total	65	100.0

Table – 02: Frequency of Alcoholic beverages dependence among study cases

Alcoholic beverages dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	7	10.8
No	58	89.2
Total	65	100.0

Table – 03: Frequency of Cannabis dependence among study cases

Cannabis dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	52	80.0
No	13	20.0
Total	65	100.0

Table – 04: Frequency of Cocaine dependence among study cases

Cocaine dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	10	15.4
No	55	84.6
Total	65	100.0

Table – 05: Frequency of Amphetamine type stimulant dependence among study cases

Amphetamine type stimulant dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	4	6.2
No	61	93.8
Total	65	100.0

Table – 06: Frequency of Inhalants dependence among study cases

Inhalants dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	5	7.7
No	60	92.3
Total	65	100.0

Table – 07: Frequency of Sedatives dependence among study cases

Sedatives dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	16	24.6
No	49	75.4
Total	65	100.0

Table – 08: Frequency of Hallucinogens dependence among study cases

Hallucinogens dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	6	9.2
No	59	90.8
Total	65	100.0

Table – 09: Frequency of Opioids dependence among study cases

Opioids dependence	Frequency	Percent
Yes	14	21.5
No	51	78.5
Total	65	100.0

DISCUSSION:

Findings from our study show an extremely high burden of psychoactive substance dependence among first-time psychiatric inpatients. Participants included 65 males with an average age of 29.2 years, the large majority being married and employed. For this group, the degree of psychoactive substance dependence is significantly greater than the rates reported in the general and student populations. Most commonly reported dependence was on cannabis (80.0%), followed by tobacco (63.1%), sedatives (24.6%), and opioids (21.5%). Cocaine, amphetamines, inhalants, and hallucinogens had lower dependence rates. In comparison, Mahmood et al. found only 26.3% tobacco use¹

(and even fewer cannabis users) among the medical students in Karachi, and Gupta et al. found among Indian medical undergraduate’s alcohol use $\geq 43.8\%$ and cannabis use $\geq 15\%$. In contrast, our clinical population, drawn from psychiatric admissions, had dependence rates that were considerably higher. This is most likely a combination of the psychiatric patients being at higher risk and the differing social circumstances. Illicit drug use is rising across the globe. In 2021 an estimated 6% of the population aged 15-64 (about 1 in 17 people, a 23% increase from 2011) used drugs.³ Pakistan follows this trend as well. In Pakistan it is estimated that 6.7 million people across all ages use drugs, of which cannabis, heroin and amphetamines are the most commonly used.⁴ Our finding of an 80%

dependence on cannabis is in line with the cannabis being the most used illicit drug in Pakistan⁴. The tobacco dependence of 63% is also in line with the local data: nearly 1 in 4 males show a smoking prevalence of 25%.^{1,3} The prominence of sedative (24.6%) and opioid (21.5%) dependence in our sample underscores a wider problem of illicit drug misuse; such rates exceed those seen in general or student populations and suggest that these substances are easily accessed, possibly as self-medication. The comparatively low rate of alcohol dependence (10.8%) likely reflects cultural and legal restrictions on alcohol in Pakistan.

We found no significant differences in substance dependence by age group, marital status, employment or socio-economic status: drug use was pervasive across all subgroups. An exception was education level: tobacco dependence was significantly higher among those with secondary or higher education, whereas opioid dependence was higher in the primary/secondary education group ($p < 0.05$). This may reflect social patterns of substance use, for example, smoking tobacco (cigarettes or sheesha) may be more common among urban/educated males, while illicit opioids (e.g. opium or prescription narcotics) might predominate in lower-educated or rural communities. These findings align with other reports that tobacco use is often widespread even in educated groups¹, though further study is needed to explain the divergent patterns for different drug classes.

The tobacco use reported in this study is consistent with literature describing tobacco use in educated groups, although further investigation is warranted to understand what drives these patterns by drug class.

Our results clinically document the association between substance use and psychiatric illness. More than half the patients (52%) presented with at least one medical comorbidity, and although mental health diagnoses were not specifically listed in this study, some studies document very high rates of psychiatric comorbidity among substance-dependent patients, and that mental health disorders are prevalent among substance-dependent individuals. Poonia et al. reported

that of Indian inpatients with substance dependence, 81% had a comorbid psychiatric disorder, the most frequent being a mood disorder. The association between substance dependence and psychopathology suggests that for many of our patients, the use of psychoactive drugs may have caused psychiatric symptoms, or, in the absence of substance use, such psychiatric symptoms may have induced substance use. Our patients' mean age is 29.2 years old so we can assume that many of these patients started using substances in their teens. The earlier individuals start using substances, the more severe the addiction and psycho social problems, if any, that ensue. This shows that there is a need for preventive strategies, especially among adolescents. Poudel & Gautam have described the need for such interventions. Psychiatric illness treatment should incorporate substance use screening, and substance use treatment should include psychiatric evaluation.

Our study also carries broader implications for public health. The exceptionally high rate of drug dependence among first-time psychiatric admissions indicates that psychiatric units may provide a pivotal opportunity for the screening and treatment of substance use disorder (SUD). Integrated treatment strategies are warranted, given the evidence that the treatment of co-occurring depression, anxiety, or personality pathology improves outcomes for SUD patients.⁵ The data also suggests that young Pakistanis' drug use is, at least in part, socially (peer influence, stress, etc.) motivated.⁴ Public health drug use prevention strategies should be directed toward education and outreach in community and school settings where the drug use initiation is likely.

The study has some limitations. The generalizability is limited since the sample size is small and confined to psychiatric wards of one military hospital. There were only male participants, so no analyses of the differences based on sex were possible. Substance use was measured with self-report and clinical interviews, which may not provide an accurate reflection of the actual substance use. The study was limited to a cross-sectional design, and so causal

relationships between mental illness and substance use cannot be established. Future studies are warranted that include larger multi-center samples, including females, and that utilize standardized instruments to determine the presence of substance use disorders and psychiatric comorbidities.

The study among first-time psychiatric inpatients revealed an alarmingly high rate of dependence on psychoactive substances, particularly cannabis and tobacco. The findings are consistent with the prevailing national trend of increasing drug use.^{3,4} They also emphasize the pressing need for the psychiatric services to incorporate the screening and treatment of SUD and the general population to strengthen the prevention activities.

CONCLUSIONS:

A high frequency of moderate to high-risk use of various psychoactive substances, including tobacco, cannabis, opioids, and sedatives, was observed among patients with first-time psychiatric admissions. These findings suggest that substance use is commonly present in this population and may be associated with psychiatric morbidity. Therefore, there is a need to enhance community awareness regarding substance use and strengthen preventive strategies, including appropriate regulatory and public health measures.

CONFLICT OF THE INTEREST:

There was no conflict of interest of any author involved in the study.

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